

The Application of Inverse Filters to 3D Microscanning of LADAR Imagery

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Abstract—Microscanning is an effective technique for reducing aliasing and increasing resolution in 2D images produced by non-coherent imaging systems. Both the aliasing reduction and resolution enhancement are accomplished by increasing the effective spatial sampling interval through sub-pixel movements of the field of view on the detector array. In this paper the authors examine (using both simulated and real data) the application of microscanning on 3D coherent imagery (with application to 2D coherent imagery). The application of Inverse filtering techniques are also examined to resolve difficulties associated with blurring by the detector and optical systems. The effects of blurring by the detector and optical system decrease image resolution when microscanning is attempted at sub-pixel movements of less than half the detector width. A discrete filter is designed using the MTF of the imaging system. This filter is then applied to images collected with a 128x128x20 FLASH 3D LADAR system. The authors also investigate the difficulties that arise when the MTF of the system is not well characterized and when image registration errors and a low signal to noise ratio are present in the system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in readout circuit technology have made nano-second image acquisition times practical. This technology has been applied to time resolved imagery of LADAR (Laser Detection And Ranging) return signals to produce image sequences that can be used to infer range resolved views

of the scene. One particular system that collects 3-D images is a FLASH LADAR imager [1], [2], [3], [4]. One drawback of this readout technology is that it has not been miniaturized to the same degree other image acquisition devices have, such as traditional silicon CCD (Charge Coupled Device) arrays. As a consequence of this the pixel pitches in FLASH LADAR imaging arrays are much larger than other imaging systems. Large pixel pitches make it difficult to sample the scene at the diffraction limit of the imaging system. This undersampling of the image produces a loss of spatial resolution.

Microscanning has been proposed as a method for attaining diffraction-limited spatial resolution from imaging systems whose spatial sampling is inadequate to achieve the diffraction-limit [5], [6]. Application of micro-scanning techniques to 3-D LADAR imaging systems imparts technical challenges not encountered in the 2-D micro-scanning problem. Chief among these problems is the fact that each 3-D image cube will phase with the target differently than others due to the fact that the time the FLASH LADAR imager begins recording data depending on when the returning pulse exceeds some predetermined threshold. This means that the individual image frames in different cubes will represent images of the target at different times. This means that the 3-D image cubes must be registered in all three dimensions as there can be line of sight variations between illuminating pulses from the LADAR system.

Once the data cubes are registered their samples can be used to populate a super lattice of pixels in a higher resolution 3-D image. It is the goal of this research to achieve a higher resolution 3-D image cube from multiple low resolution cubes via simultaneous population of a super-lattice and application of an inversion of the blurring mechanisms present in the 3-D LADAR imager. The FLASH imager is described in Section 2. Section 3 defines mathematical models for the sensor describing how the image frames are formed and their associated probability density functions. Section 4 outlines the derivation of the image reconstruction algorithm used to produce the results presented in Section 5. Section 6 serves to provide a summary of the work as well as conclusions drawn from it.

2. FLASH 3-D LADAR SYSTEM AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

The FLASH system possesses a 128 by 128 array with a ROIC (Read Out and Integration Circuit) capable of storing an image every 0.5 ns. The ROIC captures 21 images for each pulse used to interrogate the target area. The transmitted pulse has a width of approximately 7 ns from beginning to end with a width at half the maximum value of approximately 5 ns. The illuminator is a Big Sky laser with a wavelength of 1.55 μm . The receiver optics have an f-number of 2, with an aperture diameter of 10 cm. The detectors in the array have a separation of 100 μm and an effective fill factor of 100 percent via the micro-lens array used to focus light down onto the active area associated with each detector pixel.

The system was used to image a bar target that contains back surfaces at different distances from the surface containing the openings containing the bar pattern. Figure 1 shows a mesh plot containing a 3-D description of the target. The ranging performance of the 3-D LADAR system is tested in this paper by examining the differences between ranges estimated in different pixels in the array. The two back surfaces are 12 inches and 18 inches behind the front surface where the openings are that define the bar pattern. Figure 2 shows 4 images gathered by the system in the region of the bar pattern. Figure 3 plots typical return pulses as a function of time from the beginning of the range gate for the three surfaces present in the target.

Figure 1. 3-D description of the resolution target used in the LADAR imaging experiments.

3. FLASH LADAR IMAGER MODEL

The model describing the FLASH LADAR imager data is derived in this section with the ultimate goal of providing a probability density function for the ensemble of 3-D data cubes. The simulated data for each individual realization is generated by using a convolution model to compute the mean of the signal in each image of the 3-D cube based on the intensity distribution of the object in the source plane. This modeling strategy allows the algorithm to be tested under the

Figure 2. 4 images gathered by the system in the region of the bar pattern at times 0.5, 2.0, 4.0 and 6.0 ns (A, B, C, D respectively) from the beginning of the range gate while the laser pulse propagates through the target.

Figure 3. Plot of typical return pulses as a function of time from the beginning of the range gate for the three surfaces present in the target.

assumptions for which it was derived. The intensity distribution in the focal plane of the image for each return time is a convolution between the intensity of the source and a point spread function. This convolution is modeled discretely in order to facilitate the derivation of an algorithm in the computer to recover the image.

$$i_k(x, y, z) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N o(n, m, z - \delta z_k) h(x - n - \alpha_k, y - m - \beta_k),$$

where $o(n, m, z)$ is the object source intensity, $h(x, y)$ is the point spread function of the imaging system, n, m, x, y, z are integers that denote sample indices in both the image and source planes, N is the number of pixels on one side of a square detector image and $i(x, y, z)$ is the intensity in the

image plane at the detector. The parameters $\delta z_k, \alpha_k, \beta_k$ are translational shifts in the three Cartesian dimensions associated with each 3-D data cube.

The convolution model provides the mean of the probability density function (pdf) for the 3-D data. The Poisson density function is chosen to represent the PMF (Probability Mass Function) for the data cubes as it captures the discrete and non-negative nature of the measurements.

$$P[D_k(x, y, z) = d_k(x, y, z)] = \frac{i_k(x, y, z)^{d_k(x, y, z)} e^{-i_k(x, y, z)}}{d_k(x, y, z)!},$$

where, $d_k(x, y, z)$ is the measured data cube in the image plane and $D_k(x, y, z)$ is a random variable representing the image data cube. Because the noise in each voxel is assumed to be statistically independent of any others, the probability of realizing an entire set of data cubes is given by,

$$P[D = d; \forall (x, y, z, k) \in I_N] = \prod_{x=1}^N \prod_{y=1}^N \prod_{z=1}^Z \prod_{k=1}^K \frac{i_k(x, y, z)^{d_k(x, y, z)} e^{-i_k(x, y, z)}}{d_k(x, y, z)!}, \quad (1)$$

where I represents the set of integers, K is the number of data cubes used in the image reconstruction and Z is the number of samples in the range direction in the data cube.

4. IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHM

The image reconstruction algorithm is divided into two distinct steps. The first is the image registration step. In this step the translational shifts between the data cubes are computed in all three dimensions. The cubes are shifted in the range dimension so that each image in the data cubes represents a common range to the target. This is possible due to the fact that the data cubes are sampled properly in the range direction. The range to the target in each pixel is computed by finding the peak signal as a function of range. These ranges are averaged over the entire target to produce an average range that can be compared to the average range in other data cubes to compute the range offset. The cubes are then shifted in range so that image frames within all the cubes correspond to the same distance.

The shifts in the plane transverse to the optical axis of the imager cannot be so easily removed. A vector projection algorithm [7] is used to compute the shifts for each data cube by computing the relative global motion between corresponding frames in each data cube. The shifts are then averaged over all the frames in the data cube to arrive at an estimate for the shift for the entire cube. It is surmised that there is only one motion vector for the entire cube due to the fact that the acquisition time for the data cube is on the order of 10 nano-seconds. This gives very little time for motion between frames or during the acquisition of any one given frame.

The shift vectors for each cube are used in the image reconstruction step to synthesize an image for each range image

in the data cubes. The image reconstruction algorithm is derived by maximizing the natural logarithm of the likelihood function shown in equation (1) [8], [9]. Taking the natural logarithm, differentiating it with respect to one point in the true scene, $o(n_o, m_o, z_o)$ and setting the result equal to zero yields the following expression.

$$0 = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{d_k(x, y, z_o) h(x - n_o - \alpha_k, y - m_o - \beta_k)}{i_k(x, y, z_o)} - h(x - n_o - \alpha_k, y - m_o - \beta_k),$$

The dependence of this equation on the shifts in the range dimension has been eliminated due to the fact that the data cubes have been pre-registered in the range dimension. Because the point spread function is assumed to sum to one over the whole image, the triple sum can be carried out over the second term in equation (2).

$$K = \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{d_k(x, y, z_o) h(x - n_o - \alpha_k, y - m_o - \beta_k)}{i_k(x, y, z_o)}.$$

Multiplying both sides of the equation by the true image point $o(n_o, m_o, z_o)$ and dividing both sides by K ,

$$o(n_o, m_o, z_o) = o(n_o, m_o, z_o) \times \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{d_k(x, y, z_o) h(x - n_o - \alpha_k, y - m_o - \beta_k)}{K i_k(x, y, z_o)}. \quad (2)$$

This equation implies an iterative solution for the true scene. If all the terms depending on the true scene on the right are computed using an old estimate for the scene and the true scene on the left is defined as the new estimate then the following iteration is defined.

$$o^{new}(n_o, m_o, z_o) = o_{old}(n_o, m_o, z_o) \times \sum_{x=1}^N \sum_{y=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{d_k(x, y, z_o) h(x - n_o - \alpha_k, y - m_o - \beta_k)}{K i_k^{old}(x, y, z_o)}. \quad (3)$$

This iteration produces a solution for every point in the scene. A fixed number of iterations are chosen in order to provide a means for the algorithm to terminate.

5. RESULTS

This section demonstrates the performance of the algorithm on both real and simulated data. Figure 4 shows the original bar pattern used to generate the simulated image data. It is assumed that 900 photons per pixel and observation time are received from the target wherever there is a surface to reflect from. Figure 5 shows a typical frame of image plane data of the illuminated front surface of the target taken with an aperture diameter of 5 centimeters and a focal length of 10 cm. Two data cubes are simulated with a relative shift of half a pixel in the horizontal and vertical directions. Figure 6 shows a typical frame where the back surface of the target is illuminated.

Figure 4. Original bar pattern used to generate the simulated data.

Figure 6. Typical frame of simulated data showing the back surface illuminated while the front surface is not.

Figure 5. Typical frame of simulated data showing the front surface illuminated while the back surface is not.

Figure 7. Reconstruction of the target in a range slice where the front surface is illuminated.

One hundred iterations of the algorithm are applied to the simulated data cubes and used to reconstruct images of the true target. Figure 7 shows the reconstructed image of the bar target in a frame where the front surface is illuminated. Figure 8 shows the reconstructed image of the bar target in a frame where the back surface is illuminated.

The algorithm is also tested with real data as well. Figures 9 and 10 show typical frames of data where the front surface and back surface of the real target is illuminated in different image cubes. The shifts between the frames are random and on the order of many pixels. Figures 12 and ?? show images reconstructed from the low resolution frames.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The new imaging capabilities afforded by advances in high speed read out and integration technology make the 3-D mapping of targets possible at range resolutions of as little as 3 inches. This makes high resolution mapping of battlefield areas where SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) systems are denied or dont work well possible. Spatial resolution is also important, but remains a challenge for 3-D imagers as the readout and integration technology has not been miniaturized sufficiently to produce detector arrays that allow for good spatial resolution. It is demonstrated in this paper that multiple low resolution frames of 3-D data can be registered and utilized in order to reconstruct a higher resolution image of the true scene via advanced image processing algorithms.

This demonstrates how signal and image processing tech-

Figure 8. Reconstruction of the target in a range slice where the back surface is illuminated.

Figure 9. A typical frame of real data of the resolution target.

niques can be used to mitigate deficiencies in fabrication technologies that limit the performance of electro-optical components. Future research will investigate the possibility of ranging and imaging simultaneously to improve the resolution of each reconstructed image voxel produced by the post-processing algorithms. Although not necessary for images that are gathered over short atmospheric paths, blind deconvolution methods will also be researched so that blurring effects over longer ranges can be removed to improve the resolution of 3-D images.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The opinions and views expressed by the authors are not necessarily those of the Department of Defense or the United States Air Force.

Figure 10. A second typical frame of real data of the resolution target.

Figure 11. Reconstruction of the target in a range slice where the front surface is illuminated.

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Figure 12. Reconstruction of the target in a range slice where the back surface is illuminated.

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